

STEP BY STEP FACT-CHECKING CHECKLIST

QUICK WORK FLOW

SAVE THE CONTENT

Take a screenshot or copy it.

WHAT IS THE CONTENT CLAIMING?

Is it a fact, an interpretation, or a story about who is right/wrong?

Is it emotional or pushing you to agree with something?

CHECK FOR QUICK RED FLAGS

Use these five questions:

1. **Framing** — What is highlighted? What is ignored?
2. **Language** — Neutral or emotional/loaded?
3. **Balance** — Does it show more than one perspective?
4. **Consistency** — Does the answer change across tools or languages?
5. **Downstream** — Have you seen this same wording in media or social networks?

✓ **If two or more seem suspicious → verify further.**

VERIFY WITH SIMPLE TOOLS (OSINT BASICS)

Images

- Google Lens / Bing Visual Search → find originals
- TinEye → earliest version
- FotoForensics/JpegSnoop → manipulation signs

Video

- InVID → check keyframes
- YouTube DataViewer → upload time
- Deepware / Hive → deepfake checks

Text / Chatbot Answers

- GPTZero / Hive / ZeroGPT → AI-text indicators (not 100% reliable)

Source & Spread

- WHOIS / Wayback → website origin
- Hoaxy / Botometer → spread & bot signals

✓ **Look for identical posts, sudden spikes, coordinated accounts.**

LOOK FOR PATTERNS

- Same message repeated word-for-word?
- Same narrative appearing on multiple platforms at once?
- Mirrors known propaganda themes?

✓ **If yes → likely coordinated or AI-shaped.**

CHECK THE POTENTIAL IMPACT

Could it affect example:

- elections?
- identity or minority issues?
- historical memory?
- public trust in institutions?

✓ **Higher risk → act carefully.**

CHOOSE YOUR RESPONSE

- **Journalists** → verify, contextualize, or turn it into a story.
- **CSOs / educators** → use as an example in trainings or awareness posts.
- **Citizens** → do not reshare; check with a reliable source first.
- **Institutions** → monitor if it affects sensitive areas.
- **Researchers** → record as a case for tracking.

SAVE YOUR FINDINGS

- Keep the screenshot, link, and your notes.
- Tag the case (“AI-generated”, “deepfake”, “suspected bias”).

✓ **Helps build long-term awareness and comparisons.**

